

**A STUDY OF WORKING CONDITIONS ON THE HEALTH OF WOMEN
EMPLOYEE IN BPO INDUSTRY****Dr. Prakash H. Karmadkar***MMS, PhD (Management),**PS Society Institute of management & Career Development**Yamuna Nagar, Nigadi. Pune - 44.***Abstract :**

This is one side that is plus point or advantages of BPO in our country. But has any one bother to know what its limitation is? No! Now let's discuss some of it in short. We are all familiar with that BPO work 24/7. This mean it work 24 hours & 7 days in a week. These 24 hours are divided in various shift timings, which consist of 10 hrs shift generally. Such shift changes weekly, monthly or quarterly. All the employees have to adjust themselves or gets adapted to such shifts. As the value of rupee is going up and the value of dollar is declining which leads to shut-down of some BPO in Pune & PCMC area. Majority of the women employee working in BPO are of age group 21-25. With Graduation as their education. Most of the women employee have monthly shift stability. And others have weekly. Women employees spends nearly 10 Hrs for their job in BPO. Majority of the health problems are Headache & stress which almost all women employees are facing. From my dissertation study I would like to suggest that the women employee working in BPO industry has to be very careful in terms of their health issues.

Key Word :- Working Condition, Employee, BPO Industry, Health Problem**INTRODUCTION:-**

With the enactment of LPG i.e. Liberalization, Privatization & Globalization. Many new & old MNC are now are flourishing in our economy. As we know that every coin has two sides in the same way there are many advantages & disadvantages of these MNC companies & other international companies in our economy. Out of which for our study we will take BPOs i.e. Business Process Outsourcing. Growing BPO is a boon for our economy, as it provides huge employment opportunities for our young generation.

This is one side that is plus point or advantages of BPO in our country. But has any one bother to know what its limitation is? No! Now let's discuss some of it in short. We are all familiar with that BPO work 24/7. This mean it work 24 hours & 7 days in a week. These 24 hours are divided in various shift timings, which consist of 10 hrs shift generally. Such shift changes weekly, monthly or quarterly. All the employees have to adjust themselves or gets adapted to such shifts. But if we talk about the role of women employee in these shifts it is really a serious problem for them. Because these are the employee who has to manage not only their official work but also their children, their family & other

things too. In call centers today most of the women employees are attracted because of good packages provided by the BPO. In spite of all this they are facing infrastructure & health problem, which may be hazardous for their health in long run.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY: -

- 1) Growing employment opportunities in BPOs due to the package & proper infrastructure facilities
- 2) Role of women employee in call center as nearly 40% of the total employee in BPO consist of women of age between 18-30 years.
- 3) To study the impact of BPO in increasing standard of living of people by increasing national per capita income.
- 4) To know the importance of health of women employee in call center.

TABLE SHOWS THE HEALTH PROBLEMS.

Source : Own Study

This various major problems that the women employees face in BPO. The findings were as follows:

- 46% of the women employees face Digestion problem.
- 4% of the women employees face vomiting problem
- 52% of the women employees face Headache problem
- 30% of the women employees face Acidity problem
- 48% of the women employees face back pain problem
- 64% of the women employees face Stress problem

The researcher wants to find out interest of women employees behind joining BPO. The findings says that most of the women employee join BPO because of the package and infrastructure, while some women employee join BPO as it do not require any experience and minimum qualification is also desirable for them. Few women employee join BPO as they like to serve the customer and get some experience in this industry, while other join BPO as just a time pass and nothing else.

The researcher wants to find out whether women employees who are working in BPO face any other illness problem than mentioned in the questionnaire. Most of the women employee replied that they face poor eye site problem as well as weakness after joining BPO. Few employees also replied that they also face hemoglobin problem after joining BPO, which is much below the normal one.

To find out security policy in BPO for women employee, the researcher asked this question. Women employees replied that, they do feel secured during working hours but not during up-down for the duty. The reason behind that which the researcher found is cab drivers are not so reliable person. They are not regular employees of the company. A contractor is appointed by the BPO to supply these cab drivers. BPO Company is not having full information about their background & behavior.

The researcher also tries to find out whether there is a regular counseling especially for women employee in BPO. The reply to this question was not so straight forward. Some women employee replied that they do have counseling but that too related with nature of work and not for their personal improvement or personal problems. Few women employee also replied that very rarely they have counseling as the time taken by counseling is not added to their log in hours and they have to work extra to cover up their log in hours.

It is also found out that in BPO they have high expectation and standards to meet the target and customer satisfaction, for which they have strict supervision in the form of team leaders for round 10 to 15 employees in one group. When this question was asked some women employee were very disappointed as they do not prefer working under such condition where there is close supervision in fact very strict supervision for them. Some employees also replied that they can not even chat with their colleague during the working hours due to heavy call flow.

The reason behind this is to find out what are other issues, other than health in BPO. The reply for this question was almost same for all women employee. They said that poor relationship with their peers because of age group and experience the attitude doesn't match and very informal behavior prevails in the organization.

Sometime the women employee get very irate customer calls and to handle such customer is very difficult at the same time if women employee also face any personal problem they cannot even drop the call and go for a while to have a change which really irritates them.

To find out whether regular health checks up in BPO is there or not. The reply to this question is very contradictory. Women employee says that they do have regular health check up but that is just for name sake & for company profit. They do not consider women health problems if that really exist.

All of us are very cautious about our future & career & so do the women employee. When this question was asked that whether they can have a bright career in BPO the answer to this question, was that some women employee said that there is no career in BPO while some said that it is just a short term game, while others said that we can learn a lot and utilize this skill in some other industry where there is bright future.

BPO which was started in Hinjawadi name as Wipro Spectramind after that till now there are lots of ups & downs in BPO growth. The question is that how long these BPO will survive in India? The mixed reply to this question received from the women employee. Some said that it will continue for along time while some said that if health issues will not be taken care then definitely BPO has to shut down. Some said that if they reduce working hours and strict supervision then BPO can survive for along time in India.

Whether the attrition rate can be controlled by giving more pay package to women employee. The reply to this question was that employee does not think that this will work as, they said that this is not an issue the issue is nature of work & work environment. BPO industry have to modify its structure and standards in order to reduce the attrition rate.

After asking all the questions the researcher asks that then in which industry you prefer to join in future. The reply to this question was that some women employees wants to join an industry where duty hours are less, no strict supervision, future growth, health security, chances for promotion, no rotating shifts e.g. banking, teaching, insurance, home appliances company etc.

Conclusion:

1. Due to the heavy attrition rate the BPO can not manage the loss of recruiting new employees every now & then.
2. High attrition rate has also laid to poor quality productivity in terms of services provided by the employee.
3. As the value of rupee is going up and the value of dollar is declining which leads to shut-down of some BPO in Pune & PCMC area.
4. Majority of the women employee working in BPO are of age group 21-25. With Graduation as their education.
5. Most of the women employee have monthly shift stability. And others have weekly.
6. Women employees spends nearly 10 Hrs for their job in BPO.
7. Majority of the health problems are Headache & stress which almost all women employees are facing. From my dissertation study I would like to suggest that the women employee working in BPO industry has to be very careful in terms of their health issues.
 - Another point I wanted to address here is about the Companies strategies, Company should seriously take some measures in order to retain women employees in their organization.

- HR here plays a very vital role to play .HR has to look after the rate of employees already working in BPO. He/she has to be very particular about the women employee quitting the job take exit interview collect the data & find out the reasons behind that. If health & career is only the major issues because of which the employee are leaving then care should be taken in order to avoid this.
- Regular health check-ups, fun, change of system, new quality parameters, regular counseling, going for a fun or trips can be the major input which really make women employees free from stress.
- Long working hours should be avoided & as far as possible only day shift should be provided to women employees working in BPO.

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